

Impact of Work-Life Balance on Employees Performance in Pakistani Perspective

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Abstract:

In this study the relationship and impact of work life Balance on Employee Performance is investigated through four determinants of work life balance and consideration of Demographic characteristics i.e. Age, Gender, Marital status and Family role (supportive family/spouse) impact as moderating variables on the relationship of dependent and independent variables. Data is collected through structured close ended questionnaire. The sample size for this study was approximately 270. Data is analyzed through statistical techniques i.e. Pearson correlation and regression. Empirical results from data analysis has proved that there exist significant positive relationship and impact of work life balance on employee performance as well as family role and demographics plays a significant role as moderators for maintaining proper Work Life Balance in organizations. This study is limited to banking and telecom industries. This study will provides insights about proper implementation as well as management of work-life balance which can be useful for employers and managers in Telecom and Banking sector. There is very little research conducted to investigate the relationship of work-life balance and employee performance in Pakistan especially in telecom and banking industry.

Keywords Work Life Balance, Family Role, Demographics, Employee Performance, Pakistan

1. Introduction:

For every human being work and family are two integral pillars of life. From dawn to dusk, every individual finds himself trapped in a continuous strangled network of family and work tasks regardless of profession besides status in the society that engender the state of depression, anxiety and unbalanced life tasks accomplishments. When employees struggle to carry out both roles usually a state of conflict arises due to focusing on just one role more like to ignore family matters which ultimately creates stress and unease. Intensive competition and prologue of new strategies like restructuring creates ample need for every organization to manage its workforce effectively (Malik et al., 2010). That's why different techniques for achieving work-life balance for instance family and childcare programs, provision of additional leaves, opportunity of repossession of employment after leave, remunerated maternity and paternity leaves and on-job day care services are introduced. Comparative research conducted by Idrovo et al. (2012) on Spain and Latin American countries shown that 'Latin Americans' places more attention towards implementation of Work Life Balance (WLB) policies through ensuring enablers and practices by superiors then that of Spanish.

In this study impact of work life balance is investigated on employee performance through its four determinants of WLB i.e. Work-family supportive culture, Autonomy, Work-family enrichment and Flexible work arrangement and moderating role of demographic characteristics and family role in Telecom and Banking industries. Culture of any organization performs imperative function in determining the real policies implementation effectiveness and their impact on organizational and individual performance as Peters et al. (2009) in their research found work family supportive culture as an important asset of organization and a major source for obtaining Work Life Balance, reduction of burnout attitude and work family conflict in addition to achievement of work satisfaction plus higher organizational commitment. Carlson et al. (2006) also engrossed on building and nourishing positive alliance among both facets (work-family) in a way that they support each other constructively, that will bring work family enrichment because in doing so both dimensions provide productive resources to one another.

Voydanoff (2004) in his study provides reason that autonomy gives more control and independent decision making power that help out to schedule work and home tasks in a way that none of these can harm the each other (work-life) effectiveness as certain level of autonomy or independence is also essential for work life balance and work family enrichment. When we consider the impact of work family supportive culture, job autonomy and work family enrichment on work life balance we can't deny the role of flexible work arrangement like freedom to choose starting and ending time of work, facility to pick and drop kids (He, 2013), four days' work in a week (Lewis & Humbert, 2010), work hours per week or per day and leave on urgent basis that increases not only employee comfort but also enhances organization repo as according to Casper and

Harris (2008) Flexible Work Arrangements (FWA) also indicate that employers are more concerned to employees regarding their interests, welfare, comfort and their everyday jobs other than secluded work (Grover and Crooker, 1995).

1. Literature Review:

1.1 Work life Balance:

Pre-industrial societies used Greek term “olkovúfain” for work and family that comes from the words olko meaning home and voun meaning care. There is no exact or well defined definition of Work Life Balance (WLB). Different terms in different time span are used like telework, agile options for performing work (work options), work sharing, flexible work hour (per week), (Estes & Michael, 2005). Osterman (1995) defined Work Life Balance as technical and practical work structures for official and informal tasks that permit individuals to direct the worlds of work and family without any difficulty. Similarly Kar & Misra (2013) also provides definition of work life balance as blending pleasantly work and other then work activities in a way that aid people to accomplish their tasks comfortably and contentedly. Based on these definitions we can say that Work life balance is practice of providing freedom to employees to make schedules for him/herself to perform work and life commitments like family, relations, studies, accomplishment of targets and assignments, leisure pursuits, painting and travelling etc. all with comfort or simply Work Life Balance (WLB) is a fit among multiple roles of an individual. Practices enforced by Law, organizational competition policies, diverse work force and social-moral obligations are among important factors that generates need for work-life practices implementation.

2.2 Work-Family Supportive culture:

Most considerable thing when describing an organization is its “culture”. Culture depicts the real image of every organization and its values or Culture prevailed in all organizations demonstrate the real image of its values, norms moreover people behaviors and attitudes towards their organization and society as a whole. “Work Family culture” is defined as “the shared assumptions, beliefs and values regarding the extent to which an organization supports and values the integration of employees work and private lives” (Thompson et al. 1999). Supportive culture i.e. support of social group, contemporaries and supervisor plus positive perception about organization policies and their implementation aids in lessening work stress and improving employee performance creates a good judgment about use of family friendly policies like “flextime” and reduces the fear related their carrier development (Thompson et al. 1999; Thompson & Prottas, 2006) as employees perceive WLB practices as support from their organization that heightens positive attitude, commitment and organizational performance.

Findings of Cegarra et al. (2012) revealed indirect link of WLB practices on organizational outcomes and institution of “positive culture” in favor of WLB practices implementation so as to delivers the message that mangers should focus and invest more on ‘practices and culture’ that make possible the achievement of WLB. Study findings of Greenhaus et al. (2012) also shows positive and beneficial relationship between family supportive supervision and work life balance.

Employees having more propensity to characterize themselves with their organizations (Levinson, 1965) and attitude of managers, supervisors and management as a whole that molds intentions of employees (Dawley et al., 2008). Literature reveals positive liaison among supportive culture and managerial plus coworkers support and negative relation with work-life clashes (Thompson & Prottas, 2006; Jang, 2009). Managerial/Supervisor support considered as prime important aspect in supportive culture (Thomson et al. 1999; McDonald et al. 2005) because of their dynamic role in formulation and implementation of practice of WLB programmes as well as in motivation and assistance of employees to use those policies (Milliken et al. 1998). Simply Supportive culture provides encouragement, risk taking confidence, concern regarding others, peace of mind, autonomy, greater job and career satisfaction, less intention to quit, emotional wellbeing and effective team work environment that is purpose of Work Life Balance policies implementation.

2.3 Work Family Enrichment (WFE):

Frone (2003) describe 'Work-family enrichment' as an important dimension of work-life balance that means having constructive impact of one aspect on other i.e. Optimistic impact of work on family and family on work furthermore that brings productive results for employees like psychological health, job pleasure and productivity (Beutell and Wittig-Berman, 2008) and organizational loyalty (Wayne et al. 2006). Greenhaus and Powell (2006) "proposed that work-family enrichment best caught the system of the positive work-family interface and conceptualized the work-family enrichment as "the extent to which experiences in one role improve the quality of life in the other role". In point of fact "Work-family enrichment occurs when resources gained in one role either directly improve performance in the other role (instrumental) or indirectly (Carlson et al. 2006).

Several terms are used for work family enrichment in literature like "work life Synergy", "work life Facilitation", "positive Spillover", "positive Balance and Enrichment" (Greenhaus and Powell, 2006). Regarding WFE "Role expansion theory" (Marks, 1977) posits that human energy is not a finite resource but that it can expand when engaged in multiple role commitments" and "Spillover theory" (Staines, 1980) proposes that individuals who experience positive (or negative) emotions in one domain are more likely to experience a similar emotional state in another".

Model on work family enrichment presented by Greenhaus and Powell (2006) described 'flexibility and balanced schedules' as important component of work family enrichment that can helps in achievement of higher efficiency in both roles and work family synergy. 'Conservation of resources' (COR) theory presented by Hobfoll (1989) also provides many positives points for family work studies. Main focus of this theory is on "resource mobilization" because everyone in this world is in effort of get hold of resources and struggling for this throughout their life, for the reason that these family and work resources brought positives outcomes for them. And in favor of COR theory King et al. (1995) propose the "social support" as a vital resource and major predecessor of work family enrichment and family work enrichment (Greenhaus and Powell, 2006; Siu et al. 2010).

2.4 Autonomy:

Autonomy as depicted by word itself is "independence" or we can say freedom from close supervisory attention. Voydanoff (2004) and Hackman & Oldham (1976) defined job autonomy as the level of freedom and support to control jobs tasks by themselves and judgment about how to accomplish assignments prolifically. Clark (2001) defined job autonomy as "the ability to decide when, where, and how the job is to be done". Baral and Bhargava (2008) found if autonomy is endowed by resources like inventiveness and providing skills for managing time properly and with confidence, it can fetch higher level of work-family enrichment that gives direction to work life balance. Actually when employees owning the right of giving input and decision making regarding their work setup and family (personal) life decisions it reduces work family conflicts that brings work life balance eventually (Thompson and Prottas, 2006).

Theory Y also argues that "when managers have more autonomy, they have greater feelings of ownership, commitment, and responsibility, and thus perform better". Job autonomy is more central for jobs those required more control and quick decision making (high demand job). Karasek (1992) study measures also favor the point that "higher personal autonomy over how the job is done is linked to higher individual well-being".

Van & Jansen, (2006) studied the autonomy link with personality like Autonomy motive differs for every individual like some wants "empowerment on decision making" some needs autonomy (freedom) because of their bad experience with boss and some other require autonomy for fulfillment of their own desired dreams and goals in their own way with their pre-decided direction (Entrepreneurship) or combination of two or more goals. Clark (2001) also named the "Operational Flexibility" to job autonomy that is most favorable in fetching desired outcomes at work and home. Karasek's (1979) model" is also explaining the positive relationships between autonomy and Work life Balance/enrichment (positive spillover) and negative relationship with Work Family Conflict (Voydanoff 2004). Additionally job independence (Autonomy) having a constructive and

positive impact on other outcomes like more positive attitudes of employees toward their work, mental fitness, intrinsic encouragement, motivation towards work, self-driven attitude and more control over schedules regarding work and family matters and improves organizational performance (Ahuja et al. 2007; Hackman & Oldham, 1976).

2.5 Flexible work arrangements (FWA's):

Political and Economic stability, technological advancements, social and family structure changes are indispensable contributors that encouraged the introduction of flexible work arrangements. Flexible work arrangements (FWA's) defined as "the ability of individual workers to increase or decrease their working hours and to alter their work schedule (Berg et al. 2004)". Flexible work arrangements (FWA's) are also defined "as employer provided benefits that permit employees some level of control over when and where they work outside of the standard workday (Hill et al. 2003)". Flexible work arrangements are considered as "feature of high performance working" and "HRM practice" (Atkinson & Hall, 2011). Flexibility could be any type like flexibility in schedule and time table (flexitime), in locality (telehomework) and in duration of work (part-time). Usually organizations use one or bundle of these arrangements.

Lambert et al. (2008) had identified "tenure, hours worked per week, supervisory responsibilities, perceptions of work-group use and personal lifestyle" as determinants of Flexible Work Arrangements (FWA). Two fold benefits are associated with Flexible work arrangements i.e. organizational and employee benefits. Organizational Benefits takes account of "increasing competitiveness and productivity" "fostering organizational change", "improving recruitment quality and the retention of labor" and employees benefits includes the "reconciliation of work and family needs" and authorization to balance both responsibilities well (Papalexandris & Kramar, 1997).

Foremost beneficiaries of FWA are parents who are anxious about their offspring's regarding escort and safety concern (He, 2013), contract workers because they need to work for more time that disturbs their personal life but Flexible work arrangements helps them to utilize their time in effective way by proper match and balance (Sub & Sayah, 2013) and Women especially expatriates. Recently American organizations diversified work force increase due to enhancement of number of women and ethnic/racial minorities (Leicht and Fennell, 2008) paying more attention to restructure the work setup (Yang, 2008) because even employees (30%) are willing for reduction in their payments or desiring to change their current employer for the purpose of seeking Work-life Balance (Kontos et al. 1996). Study on Irish managers also favor this point (Murphy & Doherty, 2011).

2.6 Demographic characteristics:

In this study three demographic characteristics i.e. Age, Gender and Marital status are used. As Age, Gender, Marital status are three important variables as regard of WLB. On the basis these demographics work life balance practices are designed and implemented as WLB practices varies for each individual being regarding their age, gender and marital status. Women (because of dual responsibilities) especially married ones (child care responsibilities) and aged employees require more work life balance practices while Youngsters tend to use less WLB practices because they are more carrier oriented and having no or less family or dependents responsibilities as the Kaleidoscope Career Model (KCM) proposed by Mainiero and Sullivan (2006) favors the opinion that youngsters move from one job to other job to occupy more career opportunities and social relationships (Sullivan et al. 2009) but older and midlife employees are more prone towards WLB benefits.

2.7 Family Role (Supportive spouse/ Family):

Relations are always important for all human being's because of their influence on someone's life whole domains from birth to death. When family members tries to provide sympathetic boldness in stress situations, understand matters and provide consolation as well as share victory and failure both positively, all this delivers fulfillment and encouragement with work and life both that generates automatically a balance among life and

work and improves life satisfaction and higher performance at work (Greenhaus and Foley, 2007; Lamsa & Hiillos, 2008; Greenhaus and Powell, 2006). Partner's support also fails the attempt of detachment from work of his/her spouse by discussion on daily basis as when one partner dialogue other one regarding work assignments as well as problems that increases mutual trust and encouragement to do work and recover well (Hahn et al. 2014). Employees who are highly supported mentally and emotionally by their family, are more secure from burdens of conflicts arises from work family imbalance than their other co-workers (Gee et al. 2006; Day & Chamberlain, 2006).

2.8 Work life balance and employee performance:

Lazar et al. (2010) studied the work life balance as a human resource practice to enhance employee and organizational performance by identifying demographic, cultural and economic situations and related needs realization, furthermore concluded that work life balance practices not only prolific for employees themselves but also for their family, relations and society as a whole. Related research of Dissanayaka & Ali (2013) suggested that there is need of systematic efforts and continuous improvements in work life balance practices to make improvement in employee performance through Human Resource Practices i.e. flexible work arrangements, autonomy, comfortable work environment and time allocation guidance.

Actually work life balance brings multiple benefits in a mixture form like improvement in work satisfaction and loyalty, improved work performance, reduction of costs occur due to turnover, absenteeism, recruitment and selection, enhanced organizational productivity (Osoian et al. 2011), retention of talented employees, productive innovation through improved employee engagement (Benito-Osorio et al. 2015) that all directs toward desired results i.e. improved employee and organizational performance.

3. Conceptual framework

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework

3.1 Sources and scales of questionnaire items.

5-point likert scale that ranges from strongly agree to strongly disagree is used for measurement of all selected variables.

Figure 2.

Variables	Reference	No. of items
Work Life Balance	Government of Alberta, (2004)	8
Work-Family Supportive culture	Thompson, et al., (1999)	7
Flexible Work Arrangement	Al-Rajudi Olyan Kefah, (2012)	5
Autonomy	Sims, et al., (1976)	6
Work Family Enrichment	Carlson, et al., (2006)	6
Family Role	Angel & Aluja Anton, (2012);	5
Employee Performance	Green, K. W. et al., (2006)	5

Statistical Hypothesis

Conceptual model is statistically hypothesized as
 H₁: There is a significant impact of work life balance on employee performance.

H₂: There is significant impact of family role (supportive spouse/family) on relationship of work life balance and employee performance.

H₃: There is significant impact of Demographic characteristics on relationship of work life balance and employee performance.

4. Research Methodology

For analysis of conceptual Model variables, their relationship and impact on one another Quantitative approach of induction is used that is by and large includes the gathering of primary data from widespread quantities of respondents with the aim of anticipating the results to a more wide-ranging population that increase the level of reliability in research. Structured questionnaire is used to get appropriate information regarding current states of respondents which they are actually facing in their work place and this research instrument is adopted from various researches by using 5-point Likert scale that ranges from strongly agree to strongly disagree. Normality tests used in this study are goodness of fit test, Skewness - Kurtosis tests, Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, Shapiro – Wilk test. In this study anticipated sample size was approximately 270, 135 from each sector (Banking and Telecommunication) and Non-probability sampling technique is used for selection of respondents. Number of observation for each construct ranges from 15-20 as requirement for application of parametric i.e. correlation and regression test averagely observations should be 15 and ideally it can 20. Middle level manager are selected as respondents of this study from both Telecom and Banking sector of Pakistan.

5. Statistical Results

Results:

In this research age, gender, marital status were used as moderating variable under head of demographics. The total number of respondents to whom response is collected are 238, out of which 171 about 71.8% are male respondents, 67 about 28.2% are female respondents, 160 about 67.2% respondents are married and 78 about 33.8% respondents are unmarried. Age statistics shows age ranges between 20 to 30 years 41.6 %, 31.5 % have age ranges between 31 to 40 years, 41 to 50 years are 23.1 % and only 3.8 % of employee have 51 or above 51 years of age. Instrument used for data is much reliable, in light of Cronbach’s Alpha Test, with overall cronbach’s alpha value of 0.940 which is much higher than acceptable value of cronbach’s alpha.

Correlation Analysis

Table 1 shows that there exists significant positive relationship between both predictor variables (Independent and Moderator), which is 0.540 where $p < 0.01$, it means that multicollinearity was not an issue in the collected data and there also exist significant positive relationship between independent and dependent variables (Work life Balance and Employee Performance) which is 0.558 which is significant at 99 % level of confidence.

Table 1 Correlation Analysis

Correlations	Work Life Balance	Family role	Employee Performance
Work Life Balance	1	.540**	.558**
Family role	.540**	1	.571**
Employee Performance	.558**	.571**	1

Regression Analysis

Correlation matrix has proved that there exist significant positive relationship between work life balance and employee performance. To find out the actual impact of work life balance on employee performance researchers have ran the simple linear regression analysis.

Table 2 Regression Table Work Life Balance and Employee Performance Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.558 ^a	.311	.308	.51773

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Work Life Balance
- b. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

Data analysis through SPSS has proved that there exist significant positive relationship 55.8 % between work life balance and employee performance and overall impact of work life balance on employees performance in both banking and telecom industries is 31.10% as depicted value of R square in the modal summary table 2.

Moderation Analysis 1 (Family Role)

Impact of work life balance and family role on employee performance is 41.40% which is depicted by the value of R square which is 0.414 and this impact is significant as $0.000 < 0.05$ which means that 41.40 % variance in employee performance is explained by work life balance and family role collectively in banking and telecom industries. Upon entering of family role as a moderator impact of work life balance and family role on employee performance is further enhanced to 46 %, a significant positive change of 0.046, which means that now modal as a whole explained 46 % variance in the employee performance instead of 41.40 %, a significant additional increase in variance explained by 4.60 % in employee performance as depicted by value of R square change in the model summary table 3 and this change is significant as depicted by the significant F change value where $0.000 < 0.05$.

Table 3 Moderation Regression Table of Employee Performance by Family Role Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.643 ^a	.414	.409	.47851	.414	83.002	2	235	.000
2	.678 ^b	.460	.453	.46035	.046	19.908	1	234	.000

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Family Role, Work Life Balance
- b. Predictors: (Constant), Family Role, Work Life Balance, Product of Work Life Balance and Family Role

Moderation Analysis 2 (Demographics)

Results from the regression analysis through SPSS has also showed that there exist significant positive relationship about 57.30 % between work life balance, demographics and employee performance and collective impact of demographics and work life balance on employee performance is 32.80 % and this this impact is significant as $0.000 < 0.05$ in banking and telecom industries, depicted in table 4 with values of R and R square. When demographics is entered in the proposed model as a moderator, relationship between demographics, work life balance and employee performance is further strengthened (58.60 %), depicted by the value of R which is also significant as $0.019 < 0.05$. Collective impact of demographics and work life balance

on employee performance is now 34.40 %, a significant increase of about 1.60 %, depicted by the value of R square change in table 4.

Table 4 Moderation Regression Table of Employee Performance by Demographics

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.573 ^a	.328	.323	.51233	.328	57.409	2	235	.000
2	.586 ^b	.344	.335	.50739	.016	5.591	1	234	.019

a. Predictors: (Constant), Demographics, Work Life Balance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Demographics, Work Life Balance, Product of Work Life Balance and Demographics

c. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

5- Discussion and Conclusion

The aim behind this study was to find out impact of work life balance on employee performance. Work life balance was treated as an independent variable and employee performance is treated as a dependent variable in addition Demographics and Family role were used as moderating variables in this study.

It has been provided in literature that along job and work, relations are always important for all human being's because of their influence on someone's whole life domains from birth to death. As the literature study shown employees who are highly supported mentally and emotionally by their family, are more secure from burdens of conflicts arises from work family imbalance then their other co-workers. Previous researches also revealed that females are exposed and getting more work-life balance then males, as the foremost problems that reasoned mental stress and physical health illness usually lies with females. For the reason that organization's worldwide providing opportunities and driving such strategies that makes work environment congenial for their employees to add feelings of pleasure and autonomy at work. The countries like Japan, Spain and other Latin American countries seems to be at top. Likewise Pakistani organizations also putting great emphasis on this concept to satisfy their employees for achievement of higher organizational commitment and loyalty.

It was shown in literature that Supportive culture provides encouragement, risk taking confidence, concern regarding others, peace of mind, autonomy, greater job and career satisfaction, less intention to quit, emotional wellbeing and effective team work environment that is purpose of Work Life Balance policies implementation. Supervisor support (work) and Family members support (family) are vital dynamics of work family enrichment. Major beneficiary of work family enrichment are expatriates because they need more family support and encouragement to work peacefully across boundary moreover increase self-esteem. Flexible and balanced schedules are spirited aspects of work family enrichment for the reason that only balanced schedules can bring a perfect balance for managing life and work.

Other facts in literature study also provided that Autonomy provides mental fitness, intrinsic encouragement, motivation towards work, self-driven attitude, freedom to decide to individuals and more control over schedules regarding work and family matters. Through autonomy individuals learn new skills through involvement and management of multiple tasks. Flexible work arrangements (FWA) is also important determinant of Work Life Balance as it itself demonstrates aspects like autonomy, flexible work schedules, freedom to prioritize work and family responsibilities by will.

Literature also put greater emphasis on a point that employers can achieve higher level of organizational commitment if provide occasions for entertainment along work as work will be just a burden if having no thrill and enjoyment. Among work life balance practices child care facilities and parental leaves are more important WLB policies for working parents that delivers state of peace to their minds. On basis of these factors we can

say that WLB practices not only adds positive results for individual's life but also for economy as whole because healthy minds and souls generates extraordinary outcomes that boost up economic conditions ultimately.

It is also identified in literature that employee performance is a source of achieving good results from individuals and groups as a whole. Work life balance through Human Resource practices is also important way of achieving employee performance. Employee performance can furthermore be realized through positive attitude also. As individuals having strong self-attitude and personal commitment and organizational support, shows persistent results regarding their tasks and activities e.g. regular attendance, efforts for achievements and courage regarding accomplishment of targets and goals, lower job movement that results in higher performance and satisfaction at work.

This study analysis shown that Work life balance having positive impact on employee performance that happens through mutual efforts of employees and employer. Statistical results from regression analysis has proved that there exist significant positive impact of work life balance on employee performance in both banking and telecom. So it is proved "There is a significant impact of work life balance on employee performance" that is our first hypothesis.

This research moreover showed that Family role as moderator plays a significant role in modifying the relationship between work life balance and employee performance. Therefore it's proved that "There is significant impact of family role (supportive spouse/family) on relationship of work life balance and employee performance". Our third hypothesis that is impact of Demographic characteristics on relationship of work life balance is also proved as statistical results shown that moderating variable demographics has significant positive moderating impact on relationship of work life balance and employee performance.

Hence overall results in this study stretches evidences on positive work life balance practices role on employee performance alongside improved satisfaction and commitment towards organization.

In this study work life balance is predicted on four dimensions; work – life supportive culture, autonomy, work family enrichment and flexible work arrangement, in the next studies more dimension of work life balance could be incorporated in the current model to predict work life balance with more justification. Other dimension of work life balance for example optimism subculture, supportive family, personality traits, work related aspects i.e. organizational climate, working conditions etc., house hold aspects, leisure time, work load, time inflexibility and job security can also adopted for future studies.

This study is limited to banking and telecom industries, it may be extended to other industries and data is only collected from the banking and telecom industries located in Islamabad and Rawalpindi premises, in the future studies data might be collected from other cities of Pakistan with larger sample to increase generalizability of current study

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